

Data Modelling at Geospatial National Agencies related to Computable Geospatial Model

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1 Introduction

The workshop in Copenhagen provided an opportunity to study relevance and potential of computable geospatial model for provision of geographic data by national agencies. This meant to observe and analyse opportunities for delivering functional content - opportunities for delivering geospatial data associated with functionality. The functionality may provide analytical functions, visualisation capabilities, or behaviour ensuring for example authentication, transformation to a different format, different coordinate system, or encryption for transferred geo-data. In short the question is: does, for these agencies, exist any practical reason why to consider use of computable model for their data products? The main part of the analysis is in Section 4 where the issues raised at the workshop are related to the computable model.

2. Geo-data and National Agencies

Understanding processes that the national agencies perform with their data is the key for this analysis. At the workshop were representatives from the national agencies in the UK, the Netherlands, Belgium, Switzerland, Germany, Denmark, Norway, Finland and France. The role of different agencies participating at the workshop differ in how they obtain the data, and in who is the data owner. Some order acquisition of new data from third parties, some access data maintained by other agencies, and some datasets are still acquired by agencies themselves. Nevertheless, all agencies ingest some input data and manage the basic databases using normalised schemas in some central relational database systems (RDBMS).

Against the central RDBMS are developed processing pipelines that can generate the resulting geo-data products. Technically, the production of the geo-data products within these agencies can be divided into three steps.

Step 1: Data modelling resulting in the machine-readable schema of the target data model that will be used for the geo-data product.

Step 2: Transformation of the source data from RDBMS via processing pipeline into a geo-data product compliant with the machine-readable schema from Step 1.

Step 3: Deployment of the product to the provision mechanism, which makes the geo-data available for the end-users, e.g., via authenticated Web folder or via Web API.

There are two main types of data products with respect to how they are financed.

1. Data demanded by stakeholders, which have very specific need/use/requirements for the data product. Their production, maintenance and delivery is financed by the customers, the far biggest of which is the state.
2. Open-data that can be provided within the overhead in the financing provided by the state.

The data content demanded by state is usually in a specific encoding (format) for specific processes and software systems supporting operation of the state. Regarding the open-data the focus is on maximising the volume of production and on provision of the data at minimal costs. The end-user, purpose, or software system is unknown for open-data.

The choices made by agencies are based on how difficult/expensive it is to make an open-data product available, with respect to the budget provided by state. Open-data is not targeted for a specific user or purpose and the applicability and ease of adoption of the data for further use is typically out of the agencies' scope. This aspect, nevertheless, influences the number of requests per year, which the national agencies care about a lot, because it is a measure for how much is their geo-data service used. It is a measure of the service importance and indirectly of its quality.

The effect of the computable model, if applied by national agencies, should positively influence the service importance.

3. Computable Model and National Agencies

An application of the computable model is possible in the production pipeline between the central RDBMS and the end-user software application. However, there is a complex relationship between the current way of communicating geospatial data/information and the exploitation of computable model. Challenges in identifying opportunities for computable model can be divided into three levels:

1. what is different compared to the current procedures,
2. what exactly are the benefits and drawbacks of the method,
3. explain what the geospatial computable model actually is.

These are so closely associated with each other that the relevant arguments usually lay at cross-sections of two or all of these levels.

Application of the computable model in principle means new encoding for the geo-data product, which is a sensitive subject. A very good reason should exist to why a new format,

and therefore new processing pipeline, should be developed by national agency. The ability to provide functionality together with the data seems to be too abstract in order to trigger more serious considerations by agencies. The possibility of ensuring certain functionality on specific piece of data was recognised as powerful, by some engineering staff from the agencies, but it is not a sufficient argument. On the other hand selecting/betting on a specific case is not a good strategy from the computable model's perspective, because the main power and flexibility of the solution is at the more general level. The most selling examples of computable model would be those that can be used directly by end users, without any additional knowledge or software equipment, and that would provide valuable yet exclusive functionality. But they are promoting only indirectly the computable model, because they are "mere" applications of the approach. The value of the computable model is the sum of values provided by all such applications. Hence the general power and flexibility must be recognised (explained), but more concrete reasons and improvements that can be achieved with the computable model should be provided.

There are two typical application scenarios for the computable model. 1) When some service is associated with geo-data, and/or 2) when a geospatial software application needs to use different types of data models and formats. For national agencies is relevant only the first one regarding services, because they do not deal with provision of software applications, not for open-data.

All agencies provide some service associated with their geo-data products, which at least includes the functionality for transmission of data files over the Internet. However, more functionalities are typically provided by the agencies, such as registering and authenticating the users, selecting the area of interest, or selecting other parameters for searching or defining the data for download.

The computable model allows for integrated provision of these functionalities and could simplify the management of these basic, service-oriented functionalities. This means a unified management mechanism for any potential service associated with any particular data model or format. The effect of using the computable model can be seen as an emergence of a distribution framework for applicability and ease of adoption of any geo-data product including the support for more fine-grained delivery of possibly individual functional objects. The computable model does not enforce the use of computation, and can deliver just raw data when necessary - hence exactly the same data as provided today can be delivered only wrapped in a different encoding. It can, however, also include a functionality for exporting its content into various encodings such as GML or Shapefile or JPEG image. Hence the encoding of the data can be alternative on demand, when convenient.

A possible drawback is that the solution requires end-users, or end-applications to use a software package/component that enables accessing the computable objects, which are the content units of the method. Although this is an analogy to the need for a web browser in order to consume the web pages, the issue is that the end-users have to be willing to use it. It is practical to stress that the end-application (from the computable model perspective) can be a web server, which could provide the ubiquitous Web experience, but the most

powerful way is to use the platform directly via the software package. The software package is freely available including its source code and provides the means for introspection of computable objects, which carry the digital content, in a uniform representation of geographic space. The introspection of the objects is the critical difference, which allows direct computational manipulation of the content, including observations of its structure or retrieving associated resources - no parsing or other tools necessary. The introspection is omnipresent and can be valuable even when distributing just equivalent of flat files via the computational model. The introspection significantly improves productivity regarding development of new applications, and contributes to a more efficient and coherent use of open-data. Although the applicability and ease of adoption of open-data for further use is NOT the main concern for the national agencies, the application of computable objects could set a new level to high quality in service.

4. Analysis of Raised Issues

During the presentation sessions of the workshop, and especially during the breakout sessions and personal discussions many issues were mentioned by other participants that are relevant for the computable model. Selected issues were associated with the comments and/or analysis with respect to the computable model. The quoted text in italics comes from the notes recorded at the workshop.

Issue 1

At the core of model-driven approach are mappings between:

Conceptual and exchange (product) data models.

Exchange (product) data models and data models of source data sets (RDBMS).

Exchange (product) data models and existing standards (e.g. GeoSciML, CityGML).

At this core level of content production the computable model approach follows the same steps as when dealing with INSPIRE data, for example. Mappings for the computable model, however, can be written and maintain in the same language that is used for the development of the actual processing pipeline (see Step 2 in Section 2), such as Java, Python, Scala or other language. The uniform use of powerful languages mitigates mapping issues related to the technical limitations of some encodings, e.g., the constrained length of attribute names, or inability to express certain types of relationships, which may lead to loss of information and to introduction of additional set of rules about how to make the mapping possible at all. The computable model addresses also other issues related to the mappings in the model-driven approach described from Issue 3 to 8.

Issue 2

Transformation is hard!

The computable model approach makes the mapping efforts more integrated with the developments of the processing pipeline (Step 2), which aids transparency and management of the entire pipeline. This allows to focus more on the key effect of mappings, which is the transformation between the RDBMS data model and the target encoding.

Issue 3

Encodings. What is actually the intention of the INSPIRE directive – download data, but needs tools (like FME) to transform this to a format that GIS tools can use.

The computable model has its own encoding, which is qualitatively more flexible than any other encoding used today for geo-data. It is a binary encoding, which is generated from human readable language describing not only the structure and relationships of data, but possibly also algorithms for handling the data. This issue also suggests that “download data” is an incomplete intention, and that the “use” or “applicability” is equally important for any meaningful geo-data service. The dual demand of “data download” and “data applicability” is addressed by the computable model thanks to the unprecedented flexibility of the encoding with its capacity to encapsulate functional code.

Issue 4

Software innovations - More and smaller models, easier to implement, or larger model covering more use cases? Needs for both.

This issue resonates almost perfectly with the proposed solution, it de facto states what the computable model provides. Although the many smaller models does not fit well with how the national agencies work today, the point is that the computable model provides a manageable solution for provision of possibly small specialised data models and using the very same method and the same encoding for the geo-data products that are compliant with the large, standard data models like INSPIRE. It also asserts that software innovation is necessary, which is at the heart of the computable model.

Issue 5

Missing methods and tools for identifying and managing dependencies of data models and encodings.

Mappings expressed using mapping tables are not easy to maintain if one of the model changes. Development of other representations of mappings that can be linked / kept in sync with the data models. When using the computable model the encoding of the target model itself has a computational form. Therefore the target encoding can be seen as a library, and integrated development environment (IDE) can be used. Again the actual transformation of the entire processing pipeline can be coded in the same IDE, which not only simplify and unify the management of each pipeline, but the IDE also automatically identifies dependencies of the target data model. And the broken dependencies will be interactively, and automatically highlighted by IDE - no mapping tables necessary. Hence the computable model not only addresses these issues, but actually provides a simpler practical approach.

Issue 6

*Model aware update process - how to keep the data model updated - process?
Versioning, tracking of versions, influences on transformations.
Differing version concepts: release vs. revision, logical vs. physical versions.*

When data model is changed and the schema for the target data model and encoding is generated, perhaps automatically, the IDE will immediately highlight any structural and syntactic mismatches with respect to the last working version of the processing pipeline solution. The efficient utilisation of modern IDE also improves the opportunities regarding versioning. Being maintained at the same level as the code for the rest of the processing pipeline the target data model can be managed together with it in the same centralised versioning mechanism such as SVN. It is then matter of best practice how to tag the logical versions of the pipeline with the physical geo-data products generated by the pipeline.

Issue 7

- Maintenance of data models.*
- Consequences on the processes, schema.*
- Documentation of model changes.*
- Update scripts / evolution scripts, SQL.*

The use of IDE as the central tool for the management and implementation of the processing pipeline has deep consequences. The arguments used in the previous issue apply here as well. It is true, however, that updating SQL cannot be interactively validated by IDE and would require additional tests.

Issue 8

- How to formalise, interpret and validate integrity constraints?*
- Use Object Constraint Language (OCL) extensions, which are available in UML?*
- Create templates for common constraints?*

These issues may be reaching the effective limits of using UML for a general purpose feature model such as INSPIRE. It is subject for discussion whether it makes sense to use a pseudo code language in order to specify integrity constraints for such models. One reason is the mappings, which will be impossible for many popular target encodings, because they will be unable to represent the constraints. Another reason is that the pseudo code is so close to a programming language that it might be better to test and validate the specification via a reference implementation using a real programming language. Instead of using the pseudo code that can be evaluated only by error-prone humans. Nevertheless this is only a general remark on this issue. Regarding the computable model - it is a main strength of the solution to precisely specify detailed computational aspects of any data model design. Any declaration of a limited situation in which the constraint is valid along with necessary operations on the characteristic classes, or attributes that feed some conditional expression can be defined for any target data model. The computable model can handle integrity constraints in general, and it can be even suggested to be used directly as a reference solution. Mappings of these constraints coming from UML/OCL may need manual effort, but the pseudocode might be expected to be very close to the programming language of choice.

Issue 9

We use imperfect models, e.g. in terms of completeness, performance, etc.; how to make them more consistent?

Does scope of the models influence their consistency? How?

What about replacements in data models?

One approach is to strive for ease in changing data models so that they are instantly usable by end users/applications. This will allow for an efficient evolution of better and more consistent complex data models over time. Such evolution process can account both additions and replacements to data models. It is possible to assert that the smaller the scope of a data model is, the easier it is to make it consistent. With many small data models, however, it is harder to achieve consistency across the many different data models into a larger domain. Unless there is a general mechanism that systematically facilitates creation of applications using different data models. The computable model approach provides such unifying mechanism by universal encoding that can carry both structured data and functionality. The approach maximally facilitates the process of evolution, by providing a better insight along the way via evidence about what works. Although striving for the ease in changing data models is different than the standardisation approach used by INSPIRE, which in principle aims for a large fixed data model, the conceptual models elaborated during the process are immensely valuable reference for concrete data models. What is missing is a flexible encoding that can provide products using the different data models in a usable way, which is what the computable model does.

Issue 10

How to manage extensions. (INSPIRE extension).

Consistency among the model components.

Do extensible code lists break interoperability, and even software?

Do application domain extensions do the same?

National extensions.

Can general feature model-based implementations be open and extensible? and still perform?

Are generic data models useful?

Any kind of extension to a fixed data model hampers significantly applicability of the data model, and therefore it prevents geospatial apps and systems to work with each other collaboratively (interoperability). The main reason is that we have to wait until software that can work with the extension is developed, and if various systems are used we have to wait for developments in all the softwares. This reason is also valid for any change to the data model, not only for extensions, which raises the questions about how practical it is to use some general feature data model. These set of practical issues regarding implementation hurdles, client support, end user applications, were raised mainly by Ordnance Survey representatives. The computable model addresses this issue by the fact that functionality can be part of the data model and delivered as part of the content to the end user or

application. This way any change to the data model or any extension is encapsulated with the content and is usable instantly by the consumers of the content.

Issue 11

We still do not know how to manage the provision of different services powered by the processing pipelines like GenIE.

This issue identifies interest in implementation of small scale content specifications, which could provide various data services and remove the complexity regarding data usage including business terms, rights management, or entire data infrastructure. Such service could have major advantage in ease and speed of data adoption compared to the current form of provision, but as the issue states there must be an efficient way for an agency how to provide such solutions in a manageable way. The computable model has powerful capabilities in management of entire processing pipeline as described in Issue 1, 4, 5, 6 and 9. In fact its design is focused on such kind of data services.

Issue 12

Is INSPIRE compatibility possible without sharing vector data as GML files?

INSPIRE Requirements do not oblige the usage of a specific encoding, but proposes the use of GML as the default encoding.

If we use restructured/flattened versions of the INSPIRE data models how can INSPIRE conformance be ensured?

INSPIRE Themes use different formats, relevant to the thematic needs. Some themes have several use cases – the different cases would benefit from different encodings.

The recommended GML format is being produced by all national agencies in Europe, but the common software cannot work with it directly. This problem was explicitly stressed by Finnish SYKE, but had a strong trace in breakout sessions. The computable model makes it possible to include special viewers for different cases of INSPIRE datasets, for example, and thus make the data instantly usable. When inconvenient this option can be neglected, but when necessary it can be used to ensure that everything gets interpreted exactly as intended. As mentioned in Section 3 alternative encoding can be provided on demand by including functionality for exporting product's content as GML, Shapefile or JPEG image, for example.

In such cases nothing can go differently/wrong when the content is consumed by the end-user, at least not with respect to what the agency decided to provide. This way it is possible to address the issue of providing geo-data in alternative encodings that can be easily used by end-users. The INSPIRE legislation does not impose GML, hence anybody implementing INSPIRE is free to use whatever encoding format. Conformance can be ensured by immediate / on demand export to the suggested GML encoding, and computable objects can provide that functionality for all types of consumers. In a similar manner the computable model can be also used in order to guarantee other computational aspects

such as security in which features like authentication or cryptography can be applied to a specific part of the content - possibly at the level of individual objects.

Issue 13

Some model components are complex (large aggregates, but applications and users need just part of it.)

This hits the practical issue of using only parts of the geo-data product that is typically delivered as a flat file. The computable model however employs a structure of computable object-like content units. In contrast to the large chunks of geospatial data in flat files it is possible to access individual logical parts of a complex model based on its location. Furthermore the computable aspect can take care of retrieving the data for a single object-like unit by smaller parts according to the studied location and some convenient division scheme.

Issue 14

How to make dynamic, online data service on algae situation INSPIRE compliant? DATEX II (real-time road status and traffic information) is not working with INSPIRE.

Because the computable model allows for functionality to be part of the content, inclusion or reference to the dynamic data source is possible by default. The computable model also has capacity to combine several standards into a single unified encoding that can be provided by a national agency for any geo-data product. In such case Step 1 and Step 2 have to deal with multiple mappings - one for each standard, which increases the complexity of the processing workflow, but the resulting product using a single unified encoding would facilitate management of the processing workflows, as mentioned in Issue 5. If necessary, the single target encoding can have the ability to export the corresponding parts of the content back into the respective standards using their compliant formats.

Issue 15

Work with code lists and handling of updates.

Bigger code-lists.

Interaction with registries.

The code lists are in many ways similar to the dynamic online data service and technically can be treated in a similar way, using the same methods by the computable model. A difference with code list values is that they are updated by manually, perhaps less often than sensor data. Nevertheless since the change may occur at any moment in time the computable model can reuse the mechanisms for the dynamic data coming from sensors addressed in the previous issue. That will be again applied to the processing workflow with a critical effect for the end user applications. Hence the previous comment on the dynamic data services applies here as well.

Issue 16

Complexity is sometimes necessary, but complex structures are expensive to ingest. GML can handle complexity, but the lack of development on client side, to ingest complex data is a disappointment.

Vendors need assurance that the specification should not change. Challenge for INSPIRE.

Not all GIS software can read INSPIRE GML by default.

Thanks to INSPIRE more data is shared, but the provided GML is not used.

Implementing support for new encodings using complex data model is a demanding implementation endeavour for major GIS or BIM software manufacturers. Advantage of the support for computable model, once it is implemented, is that it can be re-used for any new data model in the future. It means that changes to the data model will seamlessly work without need for any change in the supported software. This capacity of the computable model is a game changer, because it cannot be addressed by the traditional static file formats such as CityGML or JPEG. Additionally the implementation is still simpler the computable model than hard-coding the full blown INSPIRE support for example in ArcGIS or QGIS. Hence the computable model can be a very attractive and flexible means for the classical GIS software to deal with the INSPIRE support, especially with respect to its future evolution.

Issue 17

Agencies should go for flexibility in the use of data.

Flexibility in the use of data is certainly important aspect, but for the highest quality in service it is necessary to add applicability of the data to the equation as well. Society is increasingly interested in immediate information or other functional value than in the fact that the data, from which the information can be obtained, is available somewhere. The computable model is designed to maximise the combination of the flexibility in use, and of the applicability of the data.

Issue 18

What is the right approach to keep pace with technological developments?

Design and maintain your production workflow so that it is the most adaptable to changes that are relevant for your technological domain. Use technological components that are most adaptable in their respective (sub-)domains. Only the most adaptable solutions survive. Identifying the most "adaptable" however, is a challenge in its own right - it implies, for example, minimum dependencies, simplicity, robustness and many other tradeoffs that might be hard to decide. It is critical to properly define what is the type of your solution first, from which domain - name as exactly as possible for what do you seek a solution. If you seek solution for mapping between different data models then search a solution that is adaptable to any possible mappings, such as ShapeChange. If you seek solution for transformation of content between encodings then search for a solution that is adaptable for transcoding from any source encoding into any target encoding. Obviously the later is

an example of a broader and more complex domain that might include entirely the first one, yet the first one ain't a complete solution for the later one. That is why ShapeChange is used as a component in HALE, which was presented as a tool for the broader domain of transformations. Even if you go for a more complex domain, as a department of a national agency for example, you still need to define this basis - the main problem with keeping pace with technology is when you need to change the basis. One difficulty is to find a definition that is as simple as possible, but not too simple either. The computable model strives for the most adaptable software design allowing for geospatial data as a service for available and easily applicable content that can be shared collaboratively across network.

Issue 19

eGovernment is a political trend to improve productivity, contribute to a more efficient and coherent public sector with a high quality in service.

This trend was stressed by Danish Geospatial Agency. We expect data in general to emerge as a service category in its own right, but the market for that is in the very early stages of development and the path that leads to that is still unclear. Clear however is the value inherent in providing data that are easy to access and easy to use without burden of the technical complexity and the underlying technology, or attempting to navigate a massive, fragmented landscapes of data. New innovations, perhaps inventions, might be necessary in order to satisfy this trend fully, and geospatial data might play exclusive role of the reference to the real world. The computable model and the effort of Grifinor Project resonates with the geospatial aspect of this trend and addresses many issues. Nevertheless there are challenges and risks remain to be overtaken in this trend. No potential solution for geospatial data as a service can claim having all the answers, not least because we do not know all the questions yet. Nobody has certainty about how to satisfy demand for more productive, efficient and coherent quality in service for geospatial data. In other words the definition of the geospatial data as a service is a new category at stake. The trend's near future will emerge businesses with issue-specific solutions on one hand, and technology developments allowing for increasingly generic and scalable solutions on the other. Both will be critical to facilitating conversations with stakeholders.

5. Grifinor Project and National Agencies

Grifinor Project is an R&D effort in providing geospatial data and information as a functional content and/or as a service. The project is focused on the concepts and software design of geospatial computable model. The ultimate goal is a software technology that is useful and provides a scalable basis for any type of geospatial data and information solutions. The best way to ensure the usefulness are real-world cases. For example, as this report shows, an opportunity for the computable model could be collaboration with a national agency towards provision of their open-data in the form of computable objects. This could be carried out independently from the workflows for production of open-data, yet contribute to emergence and evaluation of new generation of geo-data services. Based on the evaluation the feasibility of the solution for provision of geo-data by national agencies would be decided.

If information from this document is found relevant to other opportunities new conversations should follow. Further elaboration of solutions based on computable model and discussions about observations presented in this document are foreseen and welcome.